

PRACTICAL FORMS, METHODS AND MEANS OF TECHNOLOGIES OF USING INTERACTIVE METHODS IN THE FORMATION OF THE COMPETENCE OF TEACHING RUSSIAN LANGUAGE TO STUDENTS IN THE MODERN PROCESS

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Abstract. The article analyzes the use of advanced forms and methods used by Russian language teachers in the formation of students' speaking competences during the educational process. Also, the practical forms, methods and tools of the technologies of using interactive methods in the formation of the competence of teaching the Russian language to students are considered. Expediency of using interactive methods to make the lessons more colorful, to show students' speech independence, to practice communication and speech skills. The effectiveness of using interactive methods aimed at activating students' creative thinking has been proven.

Key words: Russian as a foreign language, interactive teaching methods, communication skills, stages of learning, multimedia technologies.

In modern conditions, more and more attention paid to learning foreign languages. This applies to all areas of the country's life, especially to areas where a foreign language is the key to the development of international economic, scientific and cultural relations. In this regard, additional requirements are placed on the knowledge of a foreign language by graduates of non-language higher education institutions in their professional activities.

This foreshadows the need to search for new constructive ideas to solve the problems of optimizing and activating the teaching of the Russian language, acquiring new knowledge and increasing the level of language teaching. To achieve a high level of knowledge of the Russian language, it is necessary to study fundamental languages in higher education. Therefore, in order to achieve the main goal of mastering the Russian language at a professional level, the teacher needs to master the newest methods of teaching a foreign language, special educational technologies and techniques, in order to optimally choose one or another teaching method. At the same time, the passivity and inactivity of students in the learning process remains the main problem, because all the most modern pedagogical technologies, methods and tools fully recognize the high activity of the learning and cognitive activity of the learning subjects.

Modern higher education faces the problem of forming an active position of the individual, formation of motivation and interest in students. Therefore, the processes of increasing educational and cognitive activity, taking into account the specialization and characteristics of curricula in higher education institutions, are one of the priority directions of improving the educational process.

Interactive methods are used to teach Russian speaking. In this process, the propositional method was particularly effective. The use of optimal tools in the course of working in the classroom creates an opportunity for intensive assimilation of speech in communicative dialogue, stimulates the learning process.

The modern method of teaching Russian as a foreign language is characterized by acceleration, that is, acceleration of the pace of learning, striving for greater optimization, intensification of the learning process. In order to master the Russian language in a practical way, it is necessary to understand the spoken and written speech in this language within certain limits and to be able to express one's opinion in it. A simple conclusion follows from this that the subject of teaching should not be the Russian language in general, but speech in Russian, the processes of speech formation. The difference between language and speech is clearly visible in the teaching of a foreign language, in this process, on the one hand, the language is learned, that is, there is the acquisition of language theory, on the other hand, the study of speech, that is. learning to speak, listen, read and write. Knowledge is acquired as a result of language learning, skills and competences are acquired as a result of practice.

Intensive education is considered as a specific educational system. In its framework, new principles of selection and organization of speech and language material were developed, the leaders of which are activity, personality-role, situation-thematic. A new dynamic model of teaching and managing students' communicative and educational activities was created. The ability to communicate in the Russian language is the modeling of the processes of the formation of speech words, semantic perception and communicative interaction in speech practice, and the formation of relevant mechanisms. It is of particular importance for students to master the psych techniques of speech communication and to achieve a number of pedagogical goals in teaching.

Intensive teaching of the Russian language, based on active and communicative-personal approaches, considers the practitioner of communication in a foreign language from a socio-psychological position. This is

a specially organized educational connection, during which there is an accelerated cognitive enrichment and active creative development of a person with the help of a controlled group interaction system.

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor G.A. Kitaygorodskaya said that the goal of intensive teaching of Russian as a foreign language is to acquire communication skills in Russian in the shortest possible time. According to him, the content of intensive training is the acquisition of a set of skills and competencies that are sufficient and necessary for effective activity in a particular field, as well as the acquisition of language material that ensures the formation, development and use of these skills. is mastery, and abilities work in the function of intensive education. Based on this, we will consider the conditions of the method of intensive training, in which the implementation of the conditions for the disclosure of the reserves of the student's personality is one of the following interactive methods:

- the reputation of the teacher and his creative role;
- establishing trustful relations between the teacher and students in the classroom;
- students' high emotional tone and emotional involvement in the educational process;
- highly motivated educational activities focused on educational content;
- an active approach to mastering the Russian language as a foreign language.

Interactive educational methods mean the optimal implementation of advanced trends in general pedagogy and psychology, in particular, in the context of problems of the educational role of educational processes. The main goal of teaching here is the acquisition of Russian speech by students.

It is known that foreigners who study the Russian language in their homeland become weak when they enter our country. They cannot apply what they learn. Therefore, special importance is attached to the language environment in which the acquisition of practical skills of oral communication is carried out.

In intensive conditions, interactive learning is carried out, in which the audience can use their capabilities for real communication. It is primarily about discovering and developing the abilities, skills, attitudes and relationships necessary to achieve the desired goal.

Such forms of activity are offered to students, which force them to use the Russian language and thereby learn it. Students become the authors of their own

statements; they are more likely to learn this language because they decide for themselves what they want to express. Students learn to listen to themselves as they speak. They not only express their thoughts, but also develop them further and understand better when spoken. In the process of speaking, they discover thoughts that they did not imagine at first.

Interactive learning takes into account the psychology of human relationships. The central figure here is a group of students who jointly search for a solution to a common problem, actively influence each other and the teacher, and have the opportunity to share their experiences.

The use of interactive methods in the formation of the competence of teaching Russian language to students in the rapid acquisition of foreign speech, the staging of dialogues and artificial texts offered in textbooks on technologies is important. Situations played in the classroom are repeated and performed live outside the classroom, so there is a natural reinforcement of learned speech forms.

The initial stage of teaching the Russian language as a foreign language has its own characteristics, which include the minimization of language material, its volume, readiness for perception, reproduction and free production by students, methods of its introduction and strengthening and determined by methods. That is why textbooks are so important in interactive learning. For the initial stage, they should express the model of the Russian language in the simplest linguistically, but strictly normative form, which is the core of the Russian speech system. Such a model should teach foreigners the mechanism of creating speech in Russian for basic communication needs. The concept of communicative importance cannot be defined without creating an appropriate vocabulary of elementary topics and communication situations in which these units are mainly used.

The idea of using interactive methods in the formation of modern competence of the technology textbook includes, on the one hand, modeling of the main points of the educational process, and on the other hand, modeling of speech activities carried out within the framework of the macrolanguage offered by the textbook. The specific direction of the textbook includes, first of all, the types of speech activities to be assimilated and a certain level of knowledge of the language to be achieved for each of these types.

Modeling of speech activity can be shown as modeling of speech activity according to its main types (listening, speaking, reading, writing) in the proportion necessary for the realization of specific goals.

As shown by the basic principles of humanistic psychology of foreign scientists K. Rogers, F. Perls, etc., interactive learning methods usually include discussion, heuristic conversation, brainstorming, business game, role play, etc. The choice of one or another method of education is determined based on the educational goals, the fears and expectations of the group, the teacher's mastery of one or another method, and the context of the situation. Of course, the use of these methods in the educational process implies the mutual activity of the teacher and students.

Such cooperation is carried out through the organization of speech, in which all its participants are equally active. This form of relationship does not ignore the differences in the life experience and educational level of the teacher and the student. They share ideas with equal dignity and judgment.

When using interactive teaching methods, learning becomes interesting and demanding, and students' interest in learning increases. The Russian language is of great importance in a non-linguistic university for the formation of a well-rounded and qualified specialist. In the process of working on professionally oriented texts, students receive new information and regularly fill the terminological dictionary. The practice of teaching in non-linguistic higher educational institutions indicates that there is a sufficient content base and the basis of the existing textbooks, and that the tasks of mastering the terminological vocabulary are combined. This situation shows the need to create realistic educational conditions so that every student can fully use and reveal his personal potential. To a large extent, this is helped by teaching the specific subtlety of the specialty, which mobilizes the system of knowledge, skills, abilities, mental and personal qualities necessary for the perception of new information, assimilation of foreign terminological units. is the ability to do, their use in oral or written speech. The formation of professional communicative competence occurs at the expense of filling and expanding the necessary vocabulary of students, which is a set of techniques and actions that mobilize mental stimuli in search of conditions and opportunities to fill the lack of knowledge, skills and abilities. Such strategies and effective methods are necessary for the purposeful and systematic orientation of students of national groups of non-language faculties.

Interactive education partially solves another important problem. We are talking about rest, relieving nervous stress, switching attention, changing forms of activity, etc. In this understanding, interactive education as a form of educational process is able to optimize the essence, content and structure of

pedagogical interactions. Today, interactive educational technology is of great importance in forming the competence of teaching Russian language to students, based on practical forms, methods and tools. By interactive educational technology, we understand the system of methods of organizing interaction between the teacher and students in the form of educational games, which guarantees pedagogically effective cognitive communication, as a result of which students experience a state of success conditions are created for, in educational activities and on the basis of mutual enrichment of their motivational, intellectual, emotional and other spheres. It is important to competently direct the teacher to achieve the educational goals.

In our lessons, we often use changing small groups. Aquarium technology is something like a performance where the reader acts as observer, expert, critic and analyst. A few students show the situation in the circle, and the rest observe and analyze. When studying the topic "Dialogue", we try to offer "aquarium dialogue": the text of the dialogue can be on any topic, for example, a conversation between a doctor and a patient in a hospital. The task of the actors is to convey the appropriate mood, feelings, character traits, and the task of the audience is to notice them, explain their conclusions, tell what they are based on, what they are directed towards. Brown's use of movement technology involves students moving around the classroom to gather information about the proposed topic. Often, the topics "Hobbies", "Family", "Clothes", "Home" practice all types of grammatical constructions at the same time. Etiquette dialogues, "acquaintance", "nation", "conversation in a public place", etc. topics are perfectly developed.

Thus, entering into a conversation, listening and hearing, speaking in public, discussing various professional and social issues, willingness and ability to argue - all these are the main competencies, the most difficult of which is the competent resolution of disputes related to this is an ability, it is carried out on the basis of debates, polemics and debates. When studying Russian as a foreign language in non-linguistic universities, discussions and debates are considered an effective means of improving conversational speech. These genres of speech are very important mainly from the point of view of speech culture, they provide invaluable help in developing the ability to formulate one's own position and not only to prove it, but also to convince him of its correctness, logically proven ability to use reasonable texts, select reliable arguments and formation, building them in the most useful order for the speaker, taking into account their power in relation to a certain audience (addressee), showing these arguments with

examples, using various means of demonstration that reflect the whole information, etc.

When preparing for a dialogue or monologue, conducting them and analyzing the results, students develop all the basic actions and operations characteristic of speech activity in order to implement all the norms of communication and literary language. At different stages of the monologue speech activity, the conflict participants should use written types of speech activity (when preparing statements, choosing material, etc.) and oral - dialogue or monologues. The nature of monologues and the responsibility of speech inherent in such situations is also important to develop maximum control of all components of oral speech.

Senior students are offered to choose different topics for a monologue (it can also be used for a debate or dialogue during group work or for independent work, lectures and theses presentations):

1. The most beautiful cities in the world.
2. Art is a type of modern art.
3. Wonders of the world and others.

It is also necessary to take into account the number of students in the class.

Thus, each of the discussion or discussion genres that we have considered has great potential for improving conversational speech among non-language university students, but the effectiveness of their use is largely determined by the choice of discussion or discussion based on understanding. their features and capabilities.

When using one of the interactive methods - "Incomplete sentence" technology, the student reads an incomplete sentence and is asked to quickly continue it with any word, based on the first idea that comes to mind. Sentences start very vaguely, so guys have almost unlimited opportunities to finish it. They belong to different areas of life and can cover any topic.

A similar technology "Group Story" is used very often by us. Each student adds one sentence to the beginning of the story. At a certain signal (in one minute), a sheet with an unfinished story is passed around the circle. The stories are unexpected and funny. The list of technologies that are used and very suitable for use can be continued endlessly - these include discussions, debates, seminars and, of course, games. There are many forms of role-playing games, which are one of the interactive methods in the formation of the competence of teaching the Russian language to students: presentations, interest clubs,

interviews, correspondence, roundtable discussions, press conferences, excursions, stories, reports and others. These are some examples of the use of interactive technologies in learning the Russian language. We emphasize that these technologies can significantly activate the educational process and become a condition for improving the quality of education.

Innovative technologies are associated with widespread use, which allows to fully reveal the didactic functions of these methods and realize the potential educational opportunities inherent in them. Today, due to the demand for free access to the necessary information, information centers create all the opportunities to enter scientific, cultural and information centers around the world in order to form an independent opinion within the framework of a comprehensive study of a specific problem. Thus, favorable conditions should be created for students to search for and receive information from the technological possibilities of modern means of communication, as well as to develop cognitive and communicative abilities, and to form the ability to make quick decisions in difficult situations. This process is most successful through the use of information and communication educational technologies, including specific methods and technical means of working with information (computers, audio and video equipment, telecommunication networks, etc.). This type of pedagogical technology is today called "innovative educational technologies", they continue to develop programmed educational ideas, open new technological possibilities of the educational process, for example, related to certain advantages of computers and telecommunications.

In particular, according to the latest information provided on the Internet, the largest universities in Uzbekistan are currently making maximum use of innovative technologies in the educational process; holding seminars and conferences on the introduction of innovative technologies from time to time. Specialists of higher vocational education institutions and teachers of general education schools take part in them. We emphasize that education in universities that use innovative technologies is always open to modern scientific research. The curriculum of such universities necessarily includes such forms of education as project development, training, internship in production, as well as participation in scientific organizations.

The main forms of using innovative technologies are as follows:

1) multimedia lessons conducted on the basis of computer educational programs;

2) lessons based on the author's computer presentations during lectures, seminars, laboratory work, student reports. Thus, with the help of the PowerPoint computer program, teachers organize multimedia lessons, educational modules, electronic training manuals that allow combining audiovisual information presented in various forms - graphics, slides, texts, videos, etc.;

3) testing on computers;

4) online work with telecommunication projects, audio and video resources;

5) distance education, including all forms of educational activities that are carried out without personal contact between the teacher and the student. Today, the global Internet network offers almost any educational services, from short-term training courses to full-fledged higher education programs;

6) working with an interactive tablet Smart Board;

7) voice chat over a local network used to teach phonetics. Thus, free Net Speakerphone or Speaker programs are used to conduct the conversation, which allow communication in any mode: teacher-student, student-student, conference mode.

All this is aimed at creating a foreign language environment in the process of teaching Russian as a foreign language, to achieve this, technical training manuals are used. For example, Russian language computer training programs allow the following forms of work as foreign language lessons: practicing pronunciation; work on grammatical material; expand vocabulary; learning to write; teaching monologue and dialogic speech, etc.

It is known that nowadays the Internet is more and more important in searching for information, which provides a wide range of information sources that are very necessary in the educational process. This includes basic information hosted on the network's Web and FTP servers; operational information sent by e-mail; various databases of various information centers; Information about books and magazines distributed through online stores, etc. Thus, the information resources of the Internet are organically integrated into the educational process, helping to solve various didactic tasks in the foreign language class, for example:

formation of reading skills;

fill your vocabulary in the language being studied;

improve writing skills, for example, when composing answers to your communication partners;

- Improving listening based on the original audio texts of the Internet;
- to introduce the culture, speech etiquette, speech behavior of the country of the studied language;
- improvement of monologue and dialogical speech skills;
- formation of motivation for speech activity in the Russian language and knowledge of specific features of academic writing.

In solving these problems, realistic conditions are created for students to expand their worldview, self-education, and the ability to organize independent and research work. In this regard, researcher I.G. Zakharova suggests creating an Internet library to facilitate Internet searches. However, for the effective operation of such a resource, it is important to prepare auxiliary pages containing the most valuable sources of information on the issues under study. Although these resources are not educational material, they provide an opportunity to work online with real texts that are a motivational source for students and can therefore be used in the learning process. Therefore, the opportunity to see, read, listen to and then interact with native speakers of authentic material builds independent creative and critical thinking. In this regard, electronic versions of newspapers can be offered, most of which have their own web pages. In particular, it is possible to use the pages of MEDIA LINKS, which have links to many publications, such as the Russian Library Association, the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutes, TASS Russian News Agency.

Thus, one of the interactive methods in the formation of Russian language teaching competence - the possibilities of using Internet resources are huge, because they create conditions for students located anywhere in the world to get the necessary information, be it news from the life of young people, newspapers and journal articles, regional studies, etc.

However, it is important to understand that every teacher must follow the following rule: in the educational process, the computer is not a mechanical teacher or his substitute; it is a tool that expands and expands the possibilities of his educational activity. In this case, the teacher organizes the students' learning activities, for example, tries to use situational teaching models interactively; use creative methods, including the latest methods (cases, role-playing games, business games, dialogues, debates, seminars, conferences, abstract defenses, etc.) to solve educational quality problems with the help of innovative technologies. will do.

Modern society sets even higher requirements for the level of practical knowledge of the Russian language. In this regard, the use of innovative educational technologies creates great opportunities for increasing the effectiveness of the educational process. Curriculums for the use of technologies of interactive methods in the formation of the competence of teaching Russian language to students considered in the article, practice shows that they have advantages over traditional teaching methods, because they are not only used for certain speech activities types of teaching, individual approach and increasing independence of students, allows to combine them in various combinations, but also helps to implement them. In addition, the use of innovative technologies in the process of teaching the Russian language as a foreign language allows to qualitatively improve the general cultural development of young people, contributes to further improvement of their computer skills. It helps to build language competences and increase motivation in learning Russian as a foreign language.

Therefore, the use of innovative technologies in teaching the Russian language as a foreign language has a great pedagogical potential, which makes learning a foreign language a lively creative process.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the use of interactive methods in the process of training future specialists is appropriate and justified, because they are promising technologies in teaching the Russian language, and dialogue is the leading form of educational and cognitive interactive interaction. defines as It involves the complex use of interactive methods, tools and forms of teaching the Russian language, selected in accordance with the principles of communication and cooperation in order to achieve the best result. Interactive learning also leads to the development of professional and personal qualities of students, including: creativity, critical thinking, developing the ability to discuss one's own opinion, increasing responsibility for decision-making, forming the ability to cooperate and work in a team. , develop the ability to further self-discipline, then have all the qualities that a modern professional should have. Before choosing teaching methods, the teacher of the Russian language should guide the specific tasks of the educational process, the results of which will meet the requirements for the formation of specific practical skills of students. Practical assignments based on interactive technologies allow effective learning of educational material. Thus, conditions are being created for learning the Russian language at a new and high level of quality and applying these skills in practice. Pupils learn to communicate in Russian, participate in discussions, use grammatical

constructions, activate active (passive) vocabulary in the process of communicative activity. Thus, the use of interactive technologies in the educational process helps students to smoothly transition from acquiring lexical speech skills to their inclusion in independent communicative activities at a highly professional level.

References:

1. Normamatovna, N. D. (2022). BOLALAR XARAKTERINI OCHIB BERISHDA ROMANLARNING O'RNI VA AHAMIYATI. BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 202-205.
2. Himmatova, N. N. (2023). THE EFFECT OF PERSONAL STANDARDS ON THE PROCESS OF ECONOMIC SOCIALIZATION OF THE POPULATION. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 3(7), 377-386.
3. Normamatovna, S. N., & Aminzhanovna, R. N. (2023). OPINIONS OF EASTERN THINKERS ON FAMILY AND MARRIAGE RELATIONS. JOURNAL OF SCIENCE, RESEARCH AND TEACHING, 2(7), 159-161.
4. Normamatovna, H. N. (2023). GEOMETRIK MAZMUNDAGI AMALIY HARAKTERDAGI MASALALARNI YECHISHNI O 'RGATISH METODIKASI. PEDAGOGS jurnali, 27(1), 54-57.
5. Khimmatova, N. (2023). Psychological Mechanisms in Teaching English. Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development, 2(7), 511-515.
6. Normamatovna, S. N., & Aminzhanovna, R. N. (2023). OPINIONS OF EASTERN THINKERS ON FAMILY AND MARRIAGE RELATIONS. JOURNAL OF SCIENCE, RESEARCH AND TEACHING, 2(7), 159-161.
7. Mengliyev, B. N. (2023). UMUMRIVOJLANTIRUVCHI MASHQLARNI OQITISH METODIKASI. Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities, 11(4), 450-454.
8. Mengliyev, B. (2022). PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCE OF A MODERN PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHER. Science and innovation, 1(B7), 554-556.
9. Менглиев, Б. Н., & Умиров, Ш. Б. (2020). ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ВНЕДРЕНИЯ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ НА ЗАНЯТИЯХ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРОЙ. In ИННОВАЦИОННОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ: ПОТЕНЦИАЛ НАУКИ И СОВРЕМЕННОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ (pp. 119-121).
10. Mengliyev, B. N. (2023). MAKTAB OQUVCHILARINI VATANPARVARLIK RUHIDA TARBIYLASHDA SINFDAN TASHQARI ISHLAR. THEORY AND ANALYTICAL ASPECTS OF RECENT RESEARCH, 2(14), 113-117.
11. Mengliyev, B. (2023). SOG 'LOM TURMUSH MADANIYATINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA UZVIYLIK VA UZLUKSIZLIK TEXNOLOGIYASI. Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций, 1(6 Part 6), 16-18.

12. Mengliyev, B. (2023). JISMONIY MADANIYAT IXTISOSLIGI TALABALARINING SPORT PEDAGOGIK MAHORATINI OSHIRISH MUAMMOLARI VA UNING INNOVATSION YECHIMLARI. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 2(13), 157-161.
13. Mengliyev, B. (2023). JISMONIY MADANIYAT IXTISOSLIGI TALABALARINING SPORT PEDAGOGIK MAHORATINI OSHIRISH MUAMMOLARI VA UNING INNOVATSION YECHIMLARI. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 2(13), 157-161.
14. Шамсиева, Э. Р. (2022). Клинические особенности течения различных форм ювенильного ревматоидного артрита у детей.
15. Шамсиева, Э. Р., & Миррахимова, М. Х. (2016). РОЛЬ ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПОМОЩИ В ВОСПИТАНИИ ГИПЕРАКТИВНОГО РЕБЁНКА ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА. Научная дискуссия: вопросы педагогики и психологии, (2-1), 152-156.
16. Агзамходжаева, Н. С., Файзиева, З. К., & Шамсиева, Э. Р. (2014). КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ СЛУЧАИ НАСЛЕДСТВЕННЫХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ В ПЕДИАТРИЧЕСКОЙ ПРАКТИКЕ. Новый день в медицине, (2), 90-92.
17. Абдуллаева, Д. Т., Миррахимова, М. Х., & Курбанова, Д. Р. (2016). Лечение бронхиальной астмы у детей на фоне дисплазии соединительной ткани. Научная дискуссия: вопросы медицины, (1), 24-32.
18. Turdihodjaevna, K. B., Rajabovna, S. N., & Rinatovna, S. E. (2023). BRONXOOBSTRUKTIV SINDROM KUZATILGAN BOLALARDA BRONXIAL ASTMA RIBOJLANISHING XAVF OMILLARI. Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities, 11(1), 446-453.
19. Якубов, М. С., & Мансурова, М. Я. (2013). Роль государственных служащих в процессе форсирования системы “Электронное правительство”. In XVIII Международная научно-техническая конференция “Современные средства связи (pp. 15-16).
20. Tsyrelchuk, I. N., Mamatova, N. M., & Abdul-Azalova, M. Y. (2020). Optimization of business processes via Big Data.
21. Yashnarovna, A. A. M. (2021, November). Intelligent Management Model Of Business Processes Of Production With The Use Of Fuzzy Logic Apparatus. In 2021 International Conference on Information Science and Communications Technologies (ICISCT) (pp. 1-3). IEEE.
22. Abdul-Azalova, M. Y., & Mamatova, N. M. (2021). Big data technologies in technological and business processes automatization. Big Data and Advanced Analytics, (7-1), 50-58.

23. Stoyanov, I. (2014, May). Characteristic features in management of the business processes of the organization. In BOOK OF PROCEEDINGS (p. 357).
24. Muhamediyeva, D., & Abdul-Azalova, M. (2022). Application of the theory of fuzzy logic for analysis of management systems of business processes of an enterprise. Scientific Collection «InterConf+», (22 (113)), 467-471.
25. Muhamediyeva, D., & Abdul-Azalova, M. (2022). Evaluation Of The Efficiency Of The Business Processes Of The Enterprise. Scientific Collection «InterConf», (112), 325-328.

